

Seismic fragility assessment of historical Khan structures in Izmir (Türkiye)

P. Usta ^a, S. Karimzadeh ^{b,*}, P.B. Lourenço ^b

^a Department of Civil Engineering, Isparta University of Applied Sciences, Isparta, 32200, Türkiye

^b Department of Civil Engineering, ISISE, ARISE, University of Minho, Campus de Azurém, Guimarães 4800-058, Portugal

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Real Ground Motion Records
Masonry Structures
Numerical Simulations
Fragility Analysis
Khan
Izmir (Türkiye)

ABSTRACT

The province of Izmir in Türkiye is recognized as a city renowned for its rich cultural history. The province boasts numerous Khan masonry monuments, particularly within the Kemeralti commercial district. These structures, which carry cultural significance crucial to architectural heritage, showcase distinctive construction techniques that result in varied seismic behaviors. Conducting seismic assessments of these historic monuments is vital for risk mitigation and preserving them. The initial phase of risk assessment studies involves the development of fragility curves for historical structures. Fragility curves reveal the intricate relations between seismic forces, building features, and potential damage, providing valuable information for risk assessment studies. This paper develops seismic fragility curves for historical Khan masonry monuments through data from visual field observations, structural analysis, and numerical simulations, focusing specifically on the Kemeralti commercial district of Izmir, Türkiye. Using peak ground acceleration (PGA) as the primary intensity measure, the study examines the extent of damage at various PGA levels across different limit states, including Immediate Occupancy (IO), life safety, and collapse prevention. The analysis is conducted in both the X- and Y-directions of the structure using linear time history analysis. Results show higher probabilities of exceedance (PoE) in the Y-direction (perpendicular to the main façade) of the structures compared to the X-direction, which is attributed to the configuration of the structural elements. Furthermore, a strong alignment between the predicted and observed damage patterns during the comparison for the 2020 Samos earthquake ($M_w=7.0$) is noted, indicating an IO performance level. This suggests that the Khan structures sustained only minor non-structural damage, underscoring their resilience in maintaining their structural integrity under low seismic demands. These findings emphasize the necessity of incorporating directional vulnerabilities and observed damage patterns into seismic risk assessments, advocating for targeted retrofitting strategies specifically designed to address the unique structural configurations of historical Khan monuments, thereby enhancing their resilience to higher seismic demands.

1. Introduction

Historical structures have a significant role in carrying out the cultural inheritance of a country, and they are one of the most valuable pieces of cultural accumulation [1]. There are many historical buildings, religious monuments, and ruins of our ancestors [2]. The seismic behavior of ancient masonry buildings is particularly difficult to characterize and depends on several factors, namely the properties of the materials, the geometry of the structure, the connections between structural and non-structural elements, the stiffness of the horizontal diaphragms, and building condition [3]. Moreover, many historical buildings are quite vulnerable because they were built with low-resistance materials. These buildings also have insufficient

connections among the various construction parts, such as masonry walls and floors [4,5]. Such problems in historical masonry buildings lead to an overturning collapse of the perimeter walls under horizontal earthquake records [6]. Although historic structures are highly susceptible to earthquake damage, the methods for assessing their seismic demand and capacity remain insufficient [7]

Evaluating seismic risk in masonry buildings poses a significant engineering challenge because of the diverse variables influencing their structural behavior and the inherent uncertainties that increase with earthquake intensity [8,9]. The use of fragility curves is an effective strategy for probabilistically characterizing the seismic response of masonry structures [10-12]. Numerous applications of this approach to assess masonry structures can be found in the literature, underscoring its

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: shaghkn@civil.uminho.pt (S. Karimzadeh).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2025.110208>

Received 9 August 2024; Received in revised form 17 August 2025; Accepted 11 September 2025

Available online 16 September 2025

2352-0124/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of Institution of Structural Engineers. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

significance and efficacy [13–25,12,26–30]. In particular, Lourenço and Roque [31] provided insights into the seismic vulnerability of ancient masonry structures and offered simplified methods for evaluating seismic risks, making it useful for calibrating models to assess ancient buildings. Rota et al. [12] discussed both classical and advanced approaches to structural analysis of historic masonry structures and provided model calibration techniques that can aid in accurate seismic assessment of ancient structures. Betti and Vignoli [32] emphasized the seismic behavior and numerical model calibration of an ancient basilica, providing insights that apply to various historic buildings. Valente and Milani [33] used Finite Element Method (FEM) and simplified approaches to assess the seismic vulnerability of masonry towers, focusing on calibration techniques and comparing results with observed damage. Karimzadeh et al. [22] and Karimzadeh et al. [23] examined the fragility analysis of masonry buildings in Erzincan, Türkiye, using both simulated and real ground motion records. These authors developed fragility curves to show the probability of different damage states occurring at various seismic intensity levels in the buildings. The study by Ural and Çelik [34] developed a 3D numerical model to examine the structural performance of the Tahtani Mosque in Türkiye and determined the structural damages and their causes in the body walls and vaults of the mosque. Couto et al. [16] examined the seismic performance of historic residential buildings in Lisbon city center, focusing specifically on the effect of ground settlements, and developed fragility curves to evaluate the vulnerability of these structures under seismic loads. Marotta et al. [24] developed parametric seismic fragility curves for historical churches, taking into account various parameters, such as building geometry, material properties, and construction techniques, that affect their seismic response. They measured the probability of the occurrence of different damage states under different seismic intensities. Sandoli et al. [26] developed fragility curves for Italian unreinforced masonry (URM) buildings using a hybrid method that combined empirical data and numerical analysis.

Biglari et al. [14] evaluated the structural integrity of historical mosques in Kermanshah, Iran, using field research and numerical modeling techniques. By developing fragility curves, the authors measured the probability of various damage states under different seismic intensities. Bernardo et al. [13] investigated the seismic vulnerability and fragility of pre-code masonry buildings in Portugal and conducted a comprehensive assessment using field investigations and numerical simulations to evaluate the structural integrity of these buildings under seismic loads. Usta and Bozdağ [28] developed fragility curves to conduct a seismic fragility analysis of traditional Himis structures in Türkiye and measured the probability of different damage states occurring under various seismic intensities. Bernardo et al. [20] evaluated the seismic performance and vulnerability of typological masonry buildings in the Azores, Portugal, by conducting detailed numerical simulations using simulated ground motion records. Follador et al. [17] investigated the effects of retrofit interventions on the seismic fragility of Italian masonry residential buildings. Using numerical simulations, they developed fragility curves to quantify the probability of different damage states occurring under seismic loads before and after retrofitting. Cima et al. [15] emphasized the importance of strengthening to increase the durability of historic and traditional masonry structures by developing and analyzing fragility curves and showed how different strengthening interventions can reduce the probability of damage at various seismic intensity levels. Prajapati et al. [25] used detailed numerical simulations to evaluate the structural performance of the Nepalese pagoda temple under seismic loads and assessed its seismic fragility. Cima et al. [15] developed fragility curves for the seismic evaluation of masonry buildings in historical centers prone to out-of-plane failure modes, taking into account the specific damage mechanisms that occur out-of-plane. Feizolahbeigi et al. [35] aimed to evaluate the seismic performance of a dome and surrounding minarets as secondary elements. Three-dimensional numerical models were developed according to the defined earthquake scenarios. Seismic

analyses, including pushover analysis and boundary analysis, were performed to calibrate and evaluate the seismic behavior of the entire structure.

The city of Izmir, situated in Türkiye's highest earthquake hazard zone, lies within a highly seismically active area on the western edge of the Anatolian plate. It is a city well-known for its rich cultural heritage, featuring numerous historic masonry structures, including Khans (a type of inn that functioned as a trading center and hostel). Unexpected large earthquakes can occur frequently in this region and cause serious damage to buildings. Many earthquakes with surface magnitude $M_s \geq 4.9$ have occurred near Izmir between 1900 and 2005 [36]. More recently, three earthquakes with magnitudes $M_s = 5.5, 5.9,$ and 5.9 occurred in the same region as the 2003 earthquake but did not cause any damage in Izmir [36]. In addition, on October 30, 2020, a severe earthquake of moment magnitude $M_w = 7.0$ occurred near the island of Samos, Greece, about 70 km southwest of Izmir [37]. The earthquake, which was strongly felt in Izmir, caused minor structural damage to some buildings, while 618 buildings suffered major damage, 660 buildings suffered moderate damage, and 7671 buildings suffered minor damage. 9 buildings were demolished, and there was a loss of life and property due to these demolitions [38]. In this earthquake, 118 people lost their lives, 1032 people were injured, and 9 buildings collapsed. Although the Samos earthquake was not in Izmir and was a distant earthquake, it caused damage to the structures. This event highlighted the seismic risk in the region and the importance of continued vigilance and preparedness [38].

Recent studies investigating the 2020 Samos event in the Izmir region have reported the hazard level and risk of structures in the region. Lekkas et al. [39] examined the preparedness and emergency response efforts after the 2020 Samos earthquake and evaluated the effectiveness of emergency actions in reducing the impact of the earthquake. Kiratzi et al. [40] analyzed the seismic characteristics of this event. Their study contributed to a broader understanding of seismic activity in the Aegean Sea and provided insights into the tectonic processes driving earthquakes in the region [40]. Altunisik et al. [41] reviewed the damage from this earthquake, considering the Turkish building earthquake design regulation [42]. Onat et al. [43] presented a field investigation and structural assessment of the damage caused by this earthquake. The authors emphasized the significant influence of local geological conditions on seismic damage and the need to incorporate these factors into building codes and disaster preparedness plans to mitigate earthquake risk. Askan et al. [44] presented a comprehensive analysis of the earthquake, focusing on the strong motion data collected during the event. The authors analyzed recorded ground motions to understand the characteristics of the earthquake and its impact on the surrounding region. The study examined the spatial distribution of seismic intensity and evaluated the response of various structures to earthquakes [44]. Cetin et al. [45] investigated site effects in the Izmir Bay area during this event. The authors analyzed the impact of local soil conditions on the seismic response in the study area. The results highlighted significant variations in ground shaking across different sites, emphasizing the importance of considering local geotechnical conditions in earthquake engineering and hazard mitigation.

This study makes a significant contribution by addressing the gap in the literature in seismic fragility analyses of the historical Khan structures in the Kemeralti district of Izmir. Unlike previous regional studies that have predominantly focused on geotechnical and seismological investigations or seismic damage to other building types [7,12,16,23,31], this research specifically evaluates the seismic performance of Khan structures, incorporating both X- and Y-directional responses. By doing so, it offers valuable insights that not only enhance the understanding of these structures' resilience but also guide targeted preservation and retrofitting strategies, playing a critical role in future risk assessments and restoration efforts.

A conceptual flowchart illustrating the analysis procedures adopted in this study is presented in Fig. 1. Within this framework, field

Fig. 1. Conceptual flowchart of the fragility analysis procedures adopted in this study.

observations are conducted to gather data on the structural characteristics of the selected Khans. Next, the finite element models are developed, followed by time history analysis using SAP2000 software [46]. Then, fragility curves are generated using PGA as the primary intensity measure. The results are analyzed using the impact of different PGA levels on the damage potential of the Khan structures in different structural directions (X and Y). Finally, the results are validated by comparing the predicted damage level at the intensity level of the 2020 Samos earthquake with the observed damage to various structures from the field observation.

2. Case study: historical Khans

Türkiye, which bears the traces of many civilizations and has a deep-rooted history, has a significant historical and cultural heritage in terms of its geographical location and characteristics. The built cultural heritage is of great importance in transferring historical values to future generations. There are many important historical buildings in Türkiye, and some of these buildings are located in Izmir, which was chosen as the study area. The Khans examined in this article are in the Kemeralti region, Izmir. This region is characterized by soft sedimentary layers that can significantly influence seismic responses. The soft sediments can amplify ground motion, making the structures more susceptible to seismic damage and posing unique challenges for seismic risk assessment of the Khans. Fig. 2 illustrates the spatial distribution of the six Khans considered in this study, offering insights into how their positioning on soft sediments may affect their seismic vulnerability. The figure includes an earthquake hazard map that highlights the seismicity of the region, a regional map showing the specific locations of the Khans, and individual images of each Khan. The listed Khans are Çakaloğlu, Abdurrahman, Büyük Karasmanoğlu, Demir, Ketem, and Fazlıoğlu. The map details their precise positions within the Kemeralti commercial district. The typologies, material properties, and dimensions of each Khan are critical for evaluating their structural integrity and behavior under seismic loading, as well as identifying potential retrofitting needs.

The features and plans of the Izmir historical Khan structures examined in this article are depicted in Fig. 3. This figure provides further details on the construction dates and materials of these historical

Khans. Specifically, these Khans were built in the 18th and 19th centuries using various combinations of cut stone, rubble stone, and brick. Such information is vital for understanding their geometric characteristics and construction techniques, which influence their seismic performance.

3. Dynamic analysis of historical Khans

Three primary methodologies are used for numerical modeling of masonry structures, depending on the system’s scale and the precision required: simplified micro modeling, detailed micro modeling, and macro modeling [48]. In detailed micro modeling, the material properties of masonry units and mortar are evaluated separately. Simplified micro modeling extends the masonry units to include half the mortar layer’s width, neglecting the mortar itself. In macro modeling, masonry is treated as a composite material, ignoring the distinction between units and mortar, which significantly reduces analysis time for large systems [48-50].

In the case of inadequate interconnection or interlocking of structural elements within a historical building, the potential for localized failure mechanisms to emerge in specific areas is heightened. These mechanisms often involve out-of-plane displacements, where walls or other elements move perpendicular to their plane, compromising the structural integrity and affecting the accuracy of the analysis. The distribution of mode shapes provides crucial insights into the behavior of the structure. By examining these mode shapes, it becomes possible to evaluate the performance of surrounding walls, assess the torsional rigidity (resistance to twisting), and understand how the structure responds to both in-plane (within the plane of walls) and out-of-plane deformations. This analysis helps pinpoint the structural directions or components that are either particularly vulnerable or resilient, allowing for the identification of areas that need reinforcement or are more likely to experience significant deformation during seismic events.

In this study, the preliminary assessment of the seismic vulnerability of historic masonry Khans is based on the macro-modeling approach, a convenient and widely adopted method in the literature (e.g., [51-57]). In this approach, masonry is treated as a homogeneous and isotropic continuum, representing the combined behavior of stone units and lime

Fig. 2. Hazard map of the study area, including the location of 6 selected Khans [47].

mortar, without modeling the interface joints explicitly. This simplification is particularly suitable for large-scale historical structures where detailed material data are limited, as it significantly reduces computational demand while maintaining sufficient accuracy for preliminary seismic assessments. In the finite element implementation, the primary

load-bearing walls are modeled using 8-node solid (hexahedral) elements capable of capturing three-dimensional stress states, whereas the roof systems are modeled with 4-node shell elements to represent membrane and bending behavior in thin components. This combination allows the model to differentiate the structural response of walls and

Built Date	Material Properties	
19 th Century	Cut stone, Rubble stone, and brick	<p><i>Cakaloglu Khan</i></p>
19 th Century	Smooth-cut stone, rough-cut stone, and brick	<p><i>Abdurrahman Khan</i></p>
19 th Century	Cut stone, rubble stone, and brick	<p><i>Karaosmanoğlu Khan</i></p>

Fig. 3. Features and plans of the Izmir historical Khan structures (dimensions are in meters).

Fig. 3. (continued).

roof diaphragms while preserving computational efficiency. The adopted strategy ensures that the essential stiffness and mass distribution of the Khans are accurately represented, enabling reliable estimation of their seismic demand and directional vulnerability.

Among analysis approaches, nonlinear analysis is widely regarded as the most accurate method, but it poses challenges during the preliminary assessment stages because it necessitates detailed structural information. In situations where detailed experimental and field data on structural information are limited, linear analysis can be readily applied for the preliminary evaluation of masonry structures [58]. It requires less computational power, making it a straightforward and intuitive tool for practitioners, albeit with a certain level of uncertainty. In this study, given the limited information on the Khans, we opted for a linear time history analysis approach to obtain preliminary results on the seismic demand of masonry structures. When modeling historical structures using this approach, it is crucial to accurately reflect the geometric

properties of the structure in the model.

To develop three-dimensional models of the historical Khans, SAP2000 V23 software was used while linear analysis in the time domain was performed [59]. When creating the three-dimensional model, the geometrical survey of the historical structure was used, and the cross-section, plan, and dimensions were transferred to the model through available drawings [60]. During the modeling of the historical structures, the accuracy of the three-dimensional models was also verified using photographs taken from different angles and sections of the buildings.

A macro modeling approach is employed herein in which the wall material (stone and mortar) has been modeled together as a single material property. The model consists of joints, restraints, solid, and shell elements. The primary load-bearing masonry walls were modeled using 8-node solid (hexahedral) elements, which can capture three-dimensional volumetric stress and strain states. These elements are

particularly effective in simulating the behavior of thick masonry walls, especially where out-of-plane responses are critical. In contrast, the roof systems were modeled using 4-node shell elements, which are designed to represent both membrane and plate actions in thin structural components. This combination of solid and shell elements allowed for an accurate and computationally efficient representation of the distinct structural behaviors observed in masonry wall and roof components. The supports, representing the structural foundation, are assumed to be fixed for the analysis. The damping ratio is set to be 5 % [61]. The FEM of the Khans and the number of elements used to model the Khans are presented in Fig. 4.

The size and shape of the mesh used are critical for accurately predicting stress and/or strain values in the FEM. A higher number of nodes in the FEM can lead to excessively long computation times. Therefore, mesh sizes were adjusted to achieve a suitable mesh concentration, and analyses were repeated for various scenarios. In modeling, the Sweep mesh was selected as it improves measurement distribution throughout the FEM and requires fewer nodes, as stated in the study by Karalar and Yeşil [62]. Mesh selection was tested with various mesh sizes, adjusted along the length and perpendicular to the length in width. A mesh sensitivity study was conducted by systematically varying element sizes along both the longitudinal and transverse directions, ranging from 0.80 m to 0.20 m in 0.10 m increments. As shown in Fig. 5, the natural frequencies stabilize with finer mesh resolution, indicating convergence and confirming the adequacy of the selected element size for dynamic analysis. Accordingly, the coarsest mesh yielding converged results was adopted for each structure to ensure reliable simulation outcomes without excessive computational demand [62].

To provide transparency regarding the computational resources and efficiency of the analyses, details of the software, hardware, and runtime are reported as follows: All finite element analyses and mesh sensitivity studies were performed using SAP2000 v23 on a desktop computer with an Intel Core i7–12700 CPU, 32 GB RAM, and Windows 11 OS. The mesh sensitivity analysis required approximately 4–6 h per model, depending on the number of elements, while the linear time history analyses for the full set of 30 ground motions required 6–10 h per Khan structure.

The materials used in the construction of the historic Khans of Izmir demonstrate a variety of masonry techniques that reflect regional practices and resource availability. The primary materials are cut stone, rubble, and brick, which are used in different combinations. These stones serve as the main load-bearing elements, providing compressive strength, while the bricks often contribute to infill and decorative details. The mortar used in these structures is generally lime-based, which was widely used in historic masonry because of its flexibility and compatibility with stone materials. Lime mortars, unlike modern cement-based mortars, allow for better movement accommodation and moisture exchange, which is essential for the longevity and structural integrity of masonry in seismic regions. The specific characteristics of these materials, including the type and quality of the stone and the composition of the lime mortar, significantly influence the seismic behavior of the Khans. In this study, the material definition was simplified to reflect the dominant structural components more clearly. Although the historical Khans include both cut and rubble stone, these materials were treated as a single stone type in the model due to their identical mechanical properties. Brick elements, observed in small quantities and mainly used for infill or decorative purposes, were not modeled separately. A macro modeling approach was adopted, where the masonry walls were considered as homogeneous materials. Accordingly, the analysis focused on the mechanical properties of the main load-bearing material, which is stone. An extensive literature review was conducted to determine the material properties without causing any damage to the historical texture. The properties of the covering materials used by Hrasnica and Medic [63] and Türkmən and Bilgin [64] were among the main sources for this study. Considering these references, the model types and material properties of the elements used in Khan's structural model are presented in Table 1. It is

noted that, since a linear elastic material model was adopted in SAP2000, compressive and tensile strength values were not required for the analyses. However, upon reviewing the available references, it was found that for stone masonry, a uniaxial compressive strength of 5 MPa and a null uniaxial tensile strength were reported, while no specific information was provided for the other materials (see Table 1).

The loads acting on these historical Khans are divided into two categories: gravity loads and lateral loads. Gravity loads include dead loads, while lateral loads include earthquake loads. First, a three-dimensional model was created, and gravity loads were applied. Then, predefined lateral earthquake loads were applied to the historical Khans. In the dynamic analysis of the structures, the ground was considered as a fixed support. 30 earthquake records covering different seismological characteristics and intensity levels are selected from the PEER NGA-West2 database recorded in soil classes A, B, and C [65]. Regarding the selection of accelerograms, we acknowledge that soil type A (rock) is uncommon in the vicinity of the Khans. However, this choice was made to ensure a diverse distribution of PGA values derived from global records. While many of these records correspond to soil classes B and C, those from soil class A generally exhibit lower PGA levels (approximately <0.1 g). Such lower PGA levels imply that the structures would primarily exhibit linear elastic behavior under these conditions, aligning with the linear time history analysis employed in this study. In this low PGA range, amplifications of softer soils at longer periods have minimal impact on the structural response.

Subsequently, a linear time history analysis was performed on historical Khan structures for 30 different records in the x (parallel to the main façade) and y (perpendicular to the main façade) directions. The x and y directions of the historical Khans can be seen in the finite element model in Fig. 4. The characteristics of the ground motion data are summarized in Table 2. The PGA of the selected records ranges within 0.01–0.82 g, while the PGV ranges within 2.6–79.3 cm/s.

Historical structures generally exhibit linear behavior within certain limits. Analyses conducted within these limits can adequately determine the load-carrying capacity and behavior of structural elements [66]. Linear analysis can be sufficient for an initial assessment and a quick, general evaluation of the current state of historical structures. This is particularly useful for identifying the overall stability and critical areas of the structure [67]. Although nonlinear approaches provide more realistic results in the seismic evaluation of historical structures, these approaches require detailed structural models and computational effort. In the literature, several authors, e.g. Betti et al. [68], Parisi et al. [69], Hökelekli et al. [70], Valente [56], Pouraminian [71], Cattari et al. [72], Valente [57], Xu et al. [73], and Ademović et al. [74] utilized nonlinear methods with detailed finite element models to evaluate the seismic response of historic masonry structures. On the other hand, linear analysis offers a simpler and faster calculation process [75]. Many regulations require the use of linear analysis to initially assess the safety of structures. Linear analysis helps carry out initial evaluations and determine reinforcement needs in compliance with regulations [76]. In conclusion, using linear analysis in SAP2000 for modeling and reinforcing historical structures allows for quick and effective initial assessments. This approach stands out with its compliance with regulations, computational efficiency, and sufficient accuracy within specified timeframes. Therefore, in this study, the linear analysis method was used to rapidly evaluate historical Khan structures.

4. Model verification

In general, national codes provide simplified equations for estimating the fundamental frequency of structures. These formulas are particularly useful for applications such as static seismic analyses, where the distribution of static lateral forces is determined in a simplified manner, avoiding the need for modal linear analysis [77]. Moreover, these formulas can also serve as a benchmark for model validation by enabling frequency value comparisons, ensuring that numerical models

<i>Khan's Name</i>	<i>Finite Element Model</i>
<i>Cakaloglu Khan</i> 8717 Elements, 13346 Nodes	
<i>Abdurrahman Khan</i> 9656 Elements, 11135 Nodes	
<i>Karaosmanoğlu Khan</i> 3360 Elements, 6583 Nodes	
<i>BüyükDemir Khan</i> 1292 Elements, 2615 Nodes	
<i>Keten Khan</i> 21082 Elements, 32440 Nodes	
<i>Fazlhoğlu Khan</i> 3352 Elements, 6377 Nodes	

Fig. 4. Finite element modeling of the historical Khan structures.

Fig. 5. Fundamental frequency mesh convergence analysis for historical Khan structures.

Table 1
Material properties [63,64].

Structural element	Element type	Model type	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Density (kN/m ³)	Poisson's ratio	Uniaxial Compressive Strength (MPa)	Uniaxial Tensile Strength (MPa)
Wall	Stone	Solid	3000.00	20.00	0.20	5.00	0
Roof	Covered	Shell	13000.00	2.24	0.16	-	-

accurately represent the dynamic behavior of structures. In this study, for assessing fundamental frequency, empirical formulas by ASCE 07–16 [78], C-NTC-2019 [79,80] are utilized to facilitate a simplified and pragmatic evaluation of the structural behavior of Khan structures, thereby enabling the numerical model's accuracy. We note that the most recent update of the Italian Design Code NTC-2018 [81] introduces a relationship for estimating the natural frequency of a structure based on the lateral elastic displacement at its highest point under seismic loading. This approach assumes that the displacement is determined through, at minimum, an equivalent static seismic analysis, enabling the differentiation of oscillation frequencies along the two principal directions of the structure. While this method provides a more detailed framework, this study adopts the provisions of C-NTC-2019, as they directly relate to the geometric characteristics of the analyzed structures and ensure compatibility with the other formulas and methodologies considered.

Fig. 6 provides a comparison of natural frequencies (in Hz) for several historical Khan structures calculated using four different approaches: ASCE 07–16, C-NTC-2019, and the numerical model. The empirical methods (ASCE 07–16 and C-NTC-2019) show strong alignment, with closely matching frequency values across all structures, indicating their consistency and reliability. However, the numerical model results exhibit some deviations, particularly for certain Khans, such as Abdurrahman Khan and Karaosmanoğlu Khan, where

significantly lower or higher frequencies are observed. These discrepancies highlight the ability of the numerical model to capture detailed structural characteristics, including material heterogeneity, irregular geometries, and specific boundary conditions, which are not fully addressed by simplified empirical formulas. The frequency variation among the Khans reflects differences in structural properties, with Fazlıoğlu Khan showing the highest frequencies (~8.4–8.6 Hz) due to its smaller height and increased stiffness, while Abdurrahman Khan and Demir Khan exhibit lower frequencies (~4–5 Hz), indicating more flexible structural behavior. Overall, the comparison underscores the importance of combining empirical and numerical approaches to provide both quick estimations and detailed insights into the seismic performance of masonry structures.

Finally, to assess the accuracy of the numerical models, the fundamental vibration frequencies were additionally compared with values reported in the literature. The computed frequencies range from 4.2 to 8.8 Hz and are generally consistent with those reported for similar historical masonry structures in state-of-the-art studies. According to Aksoy and Aydoğmuş [82], Şahin [83], Günaydin et al. [84], Akın and Alagöz [85], and Kılıç Demircan [86], typical fundamental frequencies for such structures fall within the range of 1.0–7.2 Hz, depending on parameters such as structural stiffness, span length, number of stories, and plan geometry. It is important to note that relatively few numerical modeling studies have specifically focused on historical Khan-type buildings.

Table 2
Ground motion data [65].

No	Event/Station	Date	Magnitude (Mw)	PGV (cm/s)	PGA (g)	Epicentral Distance (km)	Soil Class
1	Anza (Horse Canyon)	25/02/1980	4.9	2.6	0.066	12.1	A
2	Morgan Hill	24/04/1984	6.2	2.9	0.098	16.2	A
3	Coyote Lake	06/08/1979	5.7	8.3	0.132	9.3	A
4	Landers	28/06/1992	7.3	14.1	0.041	141.6	A
5	Landers	28/06/1992	7.3	20	0.146	69.2	A
6	Landers	28/06/1992	7.3	3.8	0.05	51.7	A
7	Landers	28/06/1992	7.3	3.7	0.08	42.2	A
8	Loma Prieta	18/10/1989	6.9	8.4	0.06	30.6	A
9	Loma Prieta	18/10/1989	6.9	3.5	0.073	44.8	A
10	Loma Prieta	18/10/1989	6.9	12.9	0.072	78.3	A
11	Parkfield	28/06/1966	5.6	6.8	0.0633	14.7	B
12	Morgan Hill	24/04/1984	6.2	3.6	0.1144	16.2	B
13	Kocaeli	17/08/1999	7.4	17.7	0.2188	17	B
14	Morgan Hill	24/04/1984	6.2	36.7	0.2920	11.8	B
15	Coyote Lake	06/08/1979	5.8	49.2	0.4339	3.1	B
16	Kobe	16/01/1995	6.9	79.3	0.8213	6.9	B
17	Santa Barbara	13/08/1978	7.2	16.3	0.203	14.0	B
18	N. Palm Springs	08/07/1986	6.0	41.2	0.129	13.0	B
19	Northridge	17/01/1994	6.7	17.6	0.364	37.9	B
20	Hollister	28/11/1974	5.2	9.3	0.339	14.9	B
21	Borrego Mtn	09/04/1968	6.8	26.3	0.13	46.0	C
22	Borrego Mtn	09/04/1968	6.8	2.9	0.012	217.4	C
23	Borrego Mtn	09/04/1968	6.8	2.8	0.01	195.0	C
24	Coyote Lake	06/08/1979	5.7	40.0	0.339	7.5	C
25	Coyote Lake	06/08/1979	5.7	40.0	0.272	6.0	C
26	Coyote Lake	06/08/1979	5.7	25.0	0.248	4.5	C
27	Coyote Lake	06/08/1979	5.7	15.0	0.039	31.2	C
28	Imperial Valley	15/10/1979	7.0	29.8	0.313	8.3	C
29	Imperial Valley	15/10/1979	7.0	42.8	0.327	8.5	C
30	Imperial Valley	15/10/1979	6.5	40.0	0.220	8.5	C

Fig. 6. Comparison of fundamental frequencies for Khan structures: numerical approach vs. estimated values based on ASCE 07–16 [78] and C-NTC-2019 (2019) empirical formulas.

Nevertheless, the frequency values obtained in this study align well with existing data and conform to fundamental engineering expectations, thereby supporting the reliability of the adopted modeling approach. In particular, the higher fundamental frequencies observed in stiffer structures (e.g., Fazlıoğlu and Karaosmanoğlu Khans) are consistent with theoretical predictions and were accurately captured by the models. Furthermore, the comparison between numerically derived frequencies and those estimated using empirical formulas (Fig. 6) provides additional validation of the robustness of the modeling strategy.

To ensure the reliability of the adopted macro-models, a multi-step verification and calibration process was carried out. First, the geometric accuracy of the 3D finite element models was confirmed through comparison with architectural drawings and on-site photographs. Subsequently, dynamic calibration was performed by comparing the fundamental frequencies obtained from the numerical models with those predicted by empirical formulas and with values reported in the literature for similar historical masonry structures. The computed

frequencies (4.2–8.8 Hz) showed good agreement with theoretical predictions and published data, confirming the validity of the modeling approach. In addition, a mesh sensitivity analysis was conducted to verify that the numerical results were not affected by the selected element size, thereby ensuring the stability of the fundamental frequency estimates and the overall robustness of the adopted mesh configuration.

5. Fragility analysis of historical Khans

The fragility curve of a structure represents its likelihood of reaching or exceeding various levels of damage under different levels of seismic intensity, including measures such as PGA or spectral acceleration. Seismic fragility analysis is a crucial component of the evaluation process, used to determine the likelihood of damage to structures under the influence of an earthquake. This analysis employs a statistical approach to estimate the extent to which structures might be damaged during a seismic event. It typically considers specific design features of the structures, the quality of materials used, and the current condition of the buildings under various scenarios.

For the Khan structures, seismic fragility curves were generated to illustrate the extent to which structures may be at risk in the event of an earthquake. These curves graphically represent the probability of damage to structures at a given earthquake intensity. In addition to being a part of risk assessment procedures, seismic fragility curves serve as a critical tool in the conceptualization of new buildings and the retrofitting of existing structures, helping to establish seismic resistance requirements. This analysis helps to take necessary measures to improve the seismic performance of structures [28].

5.1. Damage measures and performance levels

The first crucial stage in conducting a fragility study is defining a method for estimating the seismic damage to the building. It is important to use a damage metric that accurately captures the structural damage to a building caused by an earthquake. Numerous researchers

have proposed different damage indices and categories for buildings subjected to seismic loads. Some have employed measures based on displacement, like the maximum drift ratio, to assess the extent of damage [13,16,87–89,61,90–92].

Inter-story drift is calculated by expressing the relative lateral displacement between floors as a percentage of the story height. Building performance or damage levels, commonly referred to as "limit states," are indicated as a function of the maximum drift experienced by a building during an earthquake. FEMA 356 [76] specifies three performance levels for the URM buildings. These include Collapse Prevention (CP), Life Safety (LS), and Immediate Occupancy (IO) performance levels. Descriptions and maximum drift limits for the defined building performance levels in FEMA 356 [76] are shown in Table 3.

5.2. Methodology

Various strategies, including cloud-based methods using probabilistic seismic demand models (PSDMs) and incremental dynamic analysis (IDA), are employed to assess the fragility of engineering structures, as extensively discussed in the literature [94,95]. We note that among the available approaches, the cloud-based ground motion selection method was employed to derive fragility curves for masonry Khans in the Izmir province. To support the validity of this approach, we refer to established comparative studies. For instance, Yang et al. [96] found no statistically significant differences between fragility curves obtained via cloud and IDA methods for $PGA \leq 0.3$ g, with collapse probability differences remaining below 5%. Similarly, Mackie and Stojadinovic [97] demonstrated that the PSDM parameters derived from the cloud, IDA, and Stripe methods were closely aligned, particularly for structures exhibiting linear or mildly nonlinear behavior. At higher intensity levels, Nassirpour et al. [98] reported only minor discrepancies, with median PGA values at collapse of 1.30 g (IDA) and 1.49 g (cloud), along with comparable dispersion values. While IDA offers a more comprehensive insight into structural performance across a broad intensity range, it requires scaling of records, which can alter the frequency content and potentially affect dynamic response. In contrast, the cloud method preserves the original spectral characteristics of ground motions and provides a practical alternative when computational efficiency is a priority. Given that approximately 70% of the ground motions used in this study have PGA values below 0.3 g, the cloud approach is considered appropriate for this preliminary assessment, offering a sound balance between accuracy and efficiency. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that the approach used in this study relies on linear time history analyses, where record-to-record variability has a minimal impact, as demonstrated in Lombardi and Luca [58] and Lombardi et al. [99].

This study considers all maximum structural drift ratios within discrete intervals of the chosen ground motion intensity parameter, PGA, to conform to a normal distribution function. This enables the calculation of the probability of exceeding the defined target limit state, denoted as LS (i.e., IO, LS, and CP). Subsequently, fragility curves were generated by applying a cumulative lognormal probability distribution function to these discrete values, employing the least squares methodology. Fragility curves were then constructed by plotting the probability of exceedance (PoE) concerning the selected limit state as a function of

PGA. This process was repeated for the X and Y directions of the building at all PGA levels to derive the fragility curves for the predetermined LSs.

Fig. 7 illustrates the process used to generate the fragility curves. The maximum drift values were initially plotted for specific intervals of the chosen ground motion intensity parameter (PGA). A horizontal line on the vertical axis indicates the target limit state i (LS_i) for the maximum drift. Next, a normal distribution is employed to model the spread of the maximum drift values at each intensity level. Subsequently, the PoE of a certain limit state i at the ground motion intensity level (PGA) of j (GMI_j) is computed as follows:

$$P[D \geq LS_i | GMI_j] = a_A \tag{1}$$

where a_A represents the entire area above limit state i (LS_i) at the ground motion intensity level (PGA) of j (GMI_j). Readers are referred to Karimzadeh et al. [22], Karimzadeh et al. [100], and Karimzadeh et al. [23] for further details.

6. Results

This section summarizes the outcomes from the fragility analysis conducted on the specified structures, employing the performance levels explained in Section 5.1 and the methodology outlined in Section 5.2. Fig. 8 illustrates the fragility curves of all the structures. In modeling and analysis of historical Khans, the X direction was taken as parallel to the main façade, and the Y direction was taken as perpendicular to the main façade. Accordingly, Cakaloglu and Fazlioglu Khans have a more ductile behavior in both directions. For the other Khans, the behavior is variable and depends on the intensity level and structural direction. Notably, among the Khans investigated, namely Abdurrahman, Cakaloglu, and Demir Khans, a consistent observation is a higher PoE in the Y direction when compared to the X direction across all intensity levels. Conversely, Buyukkarasmanoglu Khan exhibits a prevailing higher PoE in the X

Fig. 7. Fragility curve generation methodology (adapted from the study of Karimzadeh et al. [23]).

Table 3
Structural performance levels in terms of drift ratios [93].

Damage levels	Structural performance levels		
	Collapse prevention (CP)	Life safety (LS)	Immediate occupancy (IO)
	Severe	Moderate	Light
Overall damage descriptions	Extensive cracking. The face course and veneer may peel off. Noticeable in-plane and out-of-plane offsets.	Extensive cracking. Noticeable in-plane offsets of masonry and minor out-of-plane offsets	Minor cracking of veneers. Minor spalling of the veneers at a few corner openings. No observable out-of-plane offsets.
Drift ratio	1.0 %	0.6 %	0.3 %

Fig. 8. Fragility Curves for (a) X and (b) Y orientations of the structure across various limit states for (a) Cakaloglu, (b) Abdurrahman, (c) Karaosmanoğlu, (d) Kucukdemir, (e) Keten, and (f) Fazlioglu Khans.

direction when compared to the Y direction. For the remaining Khans, namely Keten and Fazlioglu Khans, the structural behavior varied depending on the intensity. Specifically, the Y direction exhibits a higher risk for Keten Khan up to a certain level of PGA, particularly for IO and LS limit states. However, this trend was reversed at higher intensity levels. For the Fazlioglu Khan, the X direction generally shows higher

PoEs than the Y direction. The exception is for PGA levels greater than 0.4 g in the LS limit state, where the Y direction exhibits a higher risk.

Different responses are observed among the Khans. Demir Khan demonstrates higher PoEs for all limit states compared to the others. Conversely, Cakaloglu and Fazlioglu Khans show more ductile behavior in both directions. For the other Khans, the behavior varies depending

on the intensity level and structural direction. Notably, Abdurrahman, Cakaloglu, and Demir Khans consistently exhibit higher PoEs in the Y direction than in the X direction across all intensity levels. Conversely, Buyukkarasmanoglu Khan shows a higher PoE in the X direction than in the Y direction. For Keten and Fazlioglu Khans, the structural behavior varies with intensity. Specifically, the Y direction exhibits higher risk for Keten Khan up to a certain level of PGA, particularly for IS and LS limit states, but this trend reverses at higher intensity levels. For Fazlioglu Khan, the X direction generally shows higher PoEs, except for PGA levels greater than 0.4 g in the LS limit state, where the Y direction exhibits higher risk.

Building on the results of Fig. 8, a closer analysis is conducted for a specific intensity level, focusing on the ground motion level of DD2 (475-year return period) with a PGA of 0.46 g, as defined by the Turkish code [42]. The PoE values for the Khans in both the X and Y directions at this intensity level are calculated and presented in Table 4. The results align with the previously discussed findings, highlighting that Demir Khan and Buyukkarasmanoglu Khan exhibit critical vulnerability across all performance levels, particularly under DD2 ground motion. For the IO limit state, minimal variation in PoE is observed among the Khans. In contrast, for CP, there is a significant difference in PoE values between the Khans. Notably, the lowest PoE is recorded for Fazlioglu Khan in the Y direction at 0.35 g. These results emphasize the need for targeted retrofiting strategies that account for directional dependencies and intensity-specific risks.

In the next stage, we evaluate the predicted damage levels of the Khans for the ground shaking intensity of the 2020 Samos earthquake. For that earthquake, station 3513 recorded a PGA of 0.09 g near the Khans [37]. Fig. 9 presents the pseudo-spectral acceleration (PSA) of the 2020 Samos earthquake recorded at station 3513 in both north-south (NS) and east-west (EW) directions. It is noted that this station is the closest one to the case studies presented herein. The period values obtained from the historic Khans are as follows: Cakaloglu Khan - 0.18 s, Abdurrahman Khan - 0.24 s, Karaosmanoğlu Khan - 0.15 s, Demir Khan - 0.20 s, Keten Khan - 0.16 s, and Fazlioglu Khan - 0.11 s. When comparing the natural periods of the Khan structures (within 0.11 s-0.24 s) to the predominant periods of the earthquake (~>0.5 s) (see Fig. 9), it is evident that the structures possess shorter natural periods. This mismatch is advantageous, as resonance could have significantly amplified the shaking and increased the risk of severe damage. Consequently, the difference between the structures' natural periods and the earthquake's predominant frequencies likely mitigated the potential impact on these buildings.

Fig. 10 compares the images before and after the earthquake to assess the observed damage to these structures. The observed damage was documented through field observations conducted by the authors. It is evident that at PGA = 0.09 g, the Khans are in the IO limit state, as shown in Fig. 8, and this condition has been observed in all Khan structures. The predicted and observed results indicate that the historical Khans have reached the IO limit state. The IO limit state is a condition in which a building, despite being subjected to seismic forces, experiences only minor and non-structural cracking that does not

Fig. 9. Pseudo-spectral acceleration (PSA) of the 2020 Samos earthquake recorded at station 3513 in both north-south (NS) and east-west (EW) directions.

compromise its structural integrity or functionality, making it safe and suitable for immediate occupancy.

Moderate damage indicates broader but non-critical structural issues and has not been widely observed at this PGA level. The primary reasons are as follows: The historical Khans examined in the study were constructed using robust stone masonry techniques and exhibit high resilience in the IO limit state at low PGA levels (such as 0.09 g). Even when subjected to minor seismic forces, they generally sustain minimal damage. Although the fragility curves, which show the probability distribution of damage states, do not indicate a zero probability for moderate damage at this intensity, the predominant state remains IO because low seismic demands are insufficient to cause significant structural damage.

In the context of the historical Khans in the Kemeralti commercial district, achieving the IO limit state is significant because it ensures that these culturally and economically important structures continue to function immediately after the earthquake. The IO limit condition requires that structural elements such as walls and floors remain largely intact with minimal cracks and no significant displacement or failure. Finally, understanding the factors that affect the damage levels in historical Khans (such as the strength of stone and mortar, as well as the connections between various parts of the structure) will allow for more effective preservation efforts and provide a direction for future studies.

Lastly, as previously mentioned, it is important to note that the Samos earthquake's recorded ground motion predominantly featured far-field effects with a significant long-period frequency. Future events resulting from nearby fault ruptures can potentially alter building vulnerabilities, depending on the frequency content and the amplification of higher frequencies, which may affect the severity of damage states.

Table 4

Probability of exceedance (PoE) of the Khans in both the X and Y directions at a ground motion level of DD2 (475 years) with a PGA of 0.46 g according to Turkish code [42].

Khans	PoE		LS		CP	
			X-direction	Y-direction	X-direction	Y-direction
	X-direction	Y-direction	X-direction	Y-direction	X-direction	Y-direction
Cakaloglu Khan	0.98	0.94	0.89	0.86	0.66	0.79
Abdurrahman Khan	0.99	1.0	0.98	0.99	0.85	0.92
Buyukkarasmanoglu Khan	1.0	0.94	1.0	0.93	0.93	0.92
Demir Khan	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.99	0.96	0.99
Keten Khan	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.92	0.84
Fazlioglu Khan	1.0	0.99	0.95	0.78	0.75	0.31

Cakaloglu Khan

Abdurrahman Khan

Karaosmanoğlu Khan,

Demir Khan

Keten Khan

Fazlioglu Khan

Fig. 10. Pre (left)- and post (right)-2020 Samos earthquake images of historical Khans.

7. Conclusions

This study assesses the seismic vulnerability of the historic Khans in Kemeralti, Izmir (Türkiye), through fragility analysis. Macro-element models of the Khans were developed using SAP2000 software, with material properties derived from existing literature. Linear time history analyses were conducted based on the seismic loading specified in the Turkish seismic code. Seismic fragility curves were then generated for both the X and Y directions using peak ground acceleration (PGA) as the primary measure of seismic intensity. The predicted vulnerability levels were further evaluated by comparing them with visual field observations collected following the 2020 Samos earthquake ($M_w=7.0$), providing valuable insights into the seismic performance of these heritage buildings.

The key findings of the fragility analysis reveal that the vulnerability of the structures varies significantly across different directions (X and Y). Notably, for most structures, the Y-direction (perpendicular to the main façade) exhibited a higher probability of exceedance (PoE) compared to the X-direction (parallel to the main façade) at the equivalent PGA level. Among the Khans, Demir Khan demonstrates the highest PoEs across all limit states, indicating higher vulnerability. Conversely, Cakaloglu and Fazlioglu Khans exhibit more ductile behavior and comparatively lower PoEs in both directions. At a ground motion level of DD2 (475 years) with a PGA of 0.46 g, defined by the Turkish seismic code [42], the PoEs vary significantly among the Khans. This demonstrates a clear directional dependency in the seismic response of the structures, likely influenced by the configuration of structural elements. Such findings emphasize the critical role of structural configuration in shaping the seismic performance of buildings.

The comparison between the predicted and observed damage patterns from the 2020 Samos earthquake demonstrates the accuracy of the analysis. All structures were in immediate occupancy (IO), and the cracks observed suggest a high PoE for the IO limit state, as predicted by the fragility analysis. This alignment highlights the reliability of the vulnerability assessment for historical masonry buildings. The results provide valuable insights into the seismic behavior of these structures and support the development of targeted preservation and retrofitting strategies. Moreover, it emphasizes the need for further research on the seismic resilience of other vulnerable historical buildings in seismic regions.

While this study uses linear elastic analysis for initial assessments, it acknowledges its limitations and emphasizes the need for detailed nonlinear analysis to fully capture the seismic behavior of historical Khans. The study demonstrates that linear time history analysis, although simplified, can still provide sufficiently accurate insights into the seismic demand of complex historical structures when applied carefully with validated data. This finding supports the use of linear models for preliminary assessments, particularly for culturally significant structures with limited detailed structural information, where extensive nonlinear modeling may not be feasible. Future research will expand to include nonlinear analyses and other fragility curve generation approaches, including incremental dynamic analysis, to explore the influence of record-to-record variability on the dispersion of fragility functions using a combination of region-specific and simulated records. These analyses will address the challenge of limited real records by incorporating region-specific ground motion simulations that reflect the soil properties of the study area while also accounting for soil-structure interaction, thereby filling a significant gap in the existing literature. These approaches could enable the development of a robust validation framework for such structures by utilizing detailed analyses of the exact crack patterns.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

P. Usta: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data

curation, Conceptualization. **S. Karimzadeh:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **P. B. Lourenço:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was partly financed by FCT / MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) under the R&D Unit Institute for Sustainability and Innovation in Structural Engineering (ISISE), under reference UIDB / 04029/2020 (doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/04029/2020), and under the Associate Laboratory Advanced Production and Intelligent Systems ARISE under reference LA/P/0112/2020. This study has been partly funded by the STAND4HERITAGE project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant agreement No. 833123), as an Advanced Grant.

Data availability statement

Data supporting the reported results is available upon request from the corresponding author.

References

- [1] Teomete E, Aktas E. Structural analyses and assessment of historical Kamanli mosque in izmir, Turkey. *J Perform Constr Facil* 2010;24(4):353–64.
- [2] Mustafaraj, E., & Morina, J. (2020). Structural assessment of Mehmed Pasha Hammam in Prizren. In International Conference on Critical Thinking in Sustainable Rehabilitation and Risk Management of the Built Environment, Kosovo, November, 576–586.
- [3] Lourenço PB, Mendes N, Ramos LF, Oliveira DV. Analysis of masonry structures without box behavior. *Int J Archit Herit* 2011;5(4–5):369–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15583058.2010.528824>.
- [4] Lourenço PB. Masonry structures, overview. *Encycl Earthq Eng* 2014:1–9.
- [5] Lourenço PB, Oliveira DV, Leite JC, Ingham JM, Modena C, da Porto F. Simplified indexes for the seismic assessment of masonry buildings: an international database and validation. *Eng Fail Anal* 2013;34:585–605.
- [6] Lourenço PB. Recommendations for restoration of ancient buildings and the survival of a masonry chimney. *Constr Build Mater* 2006;20(4):239–51.
- [7] De Felice G, De Santis S, Lourenço PB, Mendes N. Methods and challenges for the seismic assessment of historic masonry structures. *Int J Archit Herit* 2016;11(1):143–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15583058.2016.1238976>.
- [8] Noor, M.A., & Kamruzzaman, M. (2011). Seismic vulnerability of historical mosques in Bangladesh. In 4th Annual Paper Meet and 1st Civil Engineering Congress, December 22–24.
- [9] Parisi F, Augenti N. Uncertainty in seismic capacity of masonry buildings. *Buildings* 2012;2(3):218–30.
- [10] Kanda J, Iwasaki R, Kobayashi H, Ellingwood BR. Probability-based seismic safety evaluation of existing buildings. *Eng Struct* 1997;19(9):708–17.
- [11] Lamego P, Lourenço PB, Sousa ML, Marques R. Seismic vulnerability and risk analysis of the old building stock at urban scale: application to a neighbourhood in Lisbon. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2017;15:2901–37.
- [12] Rota M, Penna A, Magenes G. A methodology for deriving analytical fragility curves for masonry buildings based on stochastic nonlinear analyses. *Eng Struct* 2010;32(5):1312–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2009.12.036>.
- [13] Bernardo V, Campos Costa A, Candeias P, Costa A. Seismic vulnerability assessment and fragility analysis of pre-code masonry buildings in Portugal. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2022;20(11):6229–65.
- [14] Biglari M, Formisano A, Davino A. Seismic vulnerability assessment and fragility analysis of Iranian historical mosques in kermanshah city. *J Build Eng* 2022;45:103673–873.
- [15] Cima V, Tomei V, Grande E, Imbimbo M. Fragility curves for the seismic assessment of masonry buildings in historic centers prone to out-of-plane failure modes. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2024;22(7):1801–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-023-01831-7>.
- [16] Couto R, Bento R, Gomes RC. Seismic performance and fragility curves of historical buildings in downtown Lisbon affected by settlements. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2020;18(12):5281–307. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-020-00936-0>.
- [17] Follador V, Carpanese P, Donà M, da Porto F. Effect of retrofit interventions on seismic fragility of Italian residential masonry buildings. *Int J Disaster risk Reduct* 2023;91:103668.
- [18] Gattulli V, Lofrano E, Paolone A, Piroli G. Performances of FRP reinforcements on masonry buildings evaluated by fragility curves. *Comput Struct* 2017;190:150–61.
- [19] Giresini L. Effect of dampers on the seismic performance of masonry walls assessed through fragility and demand hazard curves. *Eng Struct* 2022;261:114295.
- [20] Bernardo V, Karimzadeh S, Caicedo D, Hussaini SM, Lourenço PB. Fragility-based seismic assessment of traditional masonry buildings on Azores (Portugal) using simulated ground-motion records. *Earthq. Spectra* 2024;40(4):2836–61. <https://doi.org/10.1177/87552930241256287>.
- [21] Karimzadeh S, Funari MF, Szabó S, Hussaini SS, Rezaeian S, Lourenço PB. Stochastic simulation of earthquake ground motions for the seismic assessment of monumental masonry structures: Source-based vs site-based approaches. *Earthq Eng Struct Dyn* 2024;53(1):303–30.
- [22] Karimzadeh S, Kadaş K, Askan A, Erberik MA, Yakut A. A study on fragility analyses of masonry buildings in erzincan (Turkey) utilizing simulated and real ground motion records. *Procedia Eng* 2017;199:188–93.
- [23] Karimzadeh S, Kadaş K, Askan A, Erberik MA, Yakut A. Derivation of analytical fragility curves from SDOF models of masonry structures in erzincan (Turkey). *Earthq Struct* 2020;18(2):249–61. <https://doi.org/10.12989/eas.2020.18.2.249>.
- [24] Marotta A, Liberatore D, Sorrentino L. Parametric seismic fragility curves for historical churches. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2021;19(13):5609–41.
- [25] Prajapati S, Shrestha KC, Shakya M. Seismic fragility evaluation of the Nepalese pagoda temple: a case study of laxmi narsingha temple. *J Build Eng* 2024;87:108993.
- [26] Sandoli A, Lignola GP, Calderoni B, Prota A. Fragility curves of Italian URM buildings based on a hybrid method. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2021;19(13):4979–5013. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-021-01148-3>.
- [27] Serhal J, Deck O, Al Heib M, Chehade FH, Massih DYA. Damage of masonry structures relative to their properties: development of ground movement fragility curves. *Eng Struct* 2016;113:206–19.
- [28] Usta P, Bozdağ Ö. Seismic fragility analysis of traditional himis structures in Turkey. *Structures* 2022;43:28–39.
- [29] Vailati M, Monti G. Low-LOD fragility curves of structural units in masonry building clusters for territorial risk analysis. *Eng Struct* 2023;286:116143.
- [30] Zhang Y, Wang Z, Jiang L, Skalomenos K, Zhang D. Seismic fragility analysis of masonry structures considering the effect of mainshock-aftershock sequences. *Eng Struct* 2023;275:115287.
- [31] Lourenço PB, Roque JA. Simplified indexes for the seismic vulnerability of ancient masonry buildings. *Constr Build Mater* 2006;20(4):200–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2005.06.032>.
- [32] Betti M, Vignoli A. Numerical assessment of the static and seismic behaviour of the basilica of santa maria all'Impruneta (Italy). *Constr Build Mater* 2011;25(12):4308–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.12.028>.
- [33] Valente M, Milani G. Seismic assessment of historical masonry towers by means of simplified approaches and standard FEM. *Constr Build Mater* 2016;108:74–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.01.025>.
- [34] Ural A, Celik T. Dynamic analyses and seismic behavior of masonry minarets with single balcony. *Aksaray Univ J Sci Eng* 2018;2(1):13–27.
- [35] Feizolahbeigi A, Ramirez R, Lourenço PB. Seismic assessment of a dome structure with minarets as secondary elements: the case of soltaniyeh dome in Iran (May). *Structures*, 63. Elsevier; 2024, 106408 (May).
- [36] Usta, P. (2016). A new approximate method for earthquake behavior and seismic risk assessment of historical buildings in Izmir historical city center (Master's thesis). Suleyman Demirel University, Isparta, Turkey.
- [37] Karimzadeh S, Askan A. Simulation of strong ground motions from the October 30, 2020, samos earthquake and validation against observed records, intensity distributions, and damage in izmir, Turkey. *J Earthq Tsunami* 2024:1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1142/s1793431124500155>.
- [38] SER (2023). Samos Earthquake Report. Access: <https://daum.deu.edu.tr/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/Samos-Deprem-Raporu.pdf>, Access date: 25.07.2024.
- [39] Lekkas E, Mavroulis S, Kourou A, Manousaki M, Thoma T, Karveleas N. October 30, 2020, mw = 6.9, samos (Eastern Aegean Sea, Greece) earthquake: preparedness and emergency response for effective disaster management. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2020:1–23.
- [40] Kiratzi A, Papazachos C, Özacar A, Pinar A, Kallias C, Sopaci E. Characteristics of the 2020 samos earthquake (Aegean Sea) using seismic data. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2021:7713–35. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-021-01239-1>.
- [41] Altunisik AC, Atmaca B, Kartal ME, Günaydin M, Demir S, Uluşan A. Assessment of structural damage after October 30, 2020, aegean sea earthquake and tsunami. *J Earthq Tsunami* 2021;15(06):2150029.
- [42] TEC. Turkish Earthquake Code: Specifications for Building Design Under Earthquake Effects. Ankara 2019.
- [43] Onat O, Yon B, Öncü ME, Varolğüneş S, Karaşin A, Cemalgil S. Field reconnaissance and structural assessment of the October 30, 2020, samos, aegean sea earthquake: an example of severe damage due to the basin effect. *Nat Hazards* 2022;112(1):75–117.
- [44] Askan A, Gülerce Z, Roumelioti Z, Sotiriadis D, Melis NS, Altindal A, Akbaş B, Sopaci E, Karimzadeh S, Kalogeras I, Theodoulidis N. Samos island (Aegean Sea) M7.0 earthquake: analysis and engineering implications of strong motion data. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2022;20(14):7737–62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-021-01251-5>.

- [45] Cetin KO, Altun S, Askan A, Akgün M, Sezer A, Kınca C, Özdağ ÖC, İpek Y, Unutmaz B, Gülerce Z, Özacar AA. Site effects in izmir bay during the October 30, 2020, M7.0 samos earthquake. *Soil Dyn Earthq Eng* 2022;152:107051.
- [46] SAP2000 V23. Integrated structural analysis and design software. Berkeley, California: Computers and Structures, Inc.; 2014.
- [47] UNDRR, 2024. Access: <https://www.preventionweb.net/news/forensic-analysis-reveals-causes-building-damage-izmir-oct-30-aegean-sea-earthquake>, Access date: 26.07.2024.
- [48] Lourenço PB. Computational strategies for masonry structures (Doctoral dissertation, Delft University of Technology). Delft University Press; 1996.
- [49] Lourenço, P.B., & Calìo, I. (2018). Macro-Element Nonlinear Dynamic Analysis for the Assessment of the Seismic Vulnerability of Masonry Structures.
- [50] Marques R, Lourenço PB. Unreinforced and confined masonry buildings in seismic regions: validation of macro-element models and cost analysis. *Eng Struct* 2014; 64:52–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2014.01.003>.
- [51] Da Silva LC, Milani G. A FE-based macro-element for the assessment of masonry structures: linear static, vibration, and non-linear cyclic analyses. *Appl Sci* 2022; 12(3):1248.
- [52] Funari MF, Silva LC, Savalle N, Lourenço PB. A concurrent micro/macro FE-model optimized with a limit analysis tool for the assessment of dry-joint masonry structures. *Int J Multiscale Comput Eng* 2022;20(5).
- [53] Gürbüz M, Kocaman İ. Enhancing seismic resilience: a proposed reinforcement technique for historical minarets. *Eng Fail Anal* 2024;156:107832.
- [54] Pantò B, Cannizzaro F, Caddemi S, Calìo I. 3D macro-element modelling approach for seismic assessment of historical masonry churches. *Adv Eng Softw* 2016;97: 40–59.
- [55] Sangiorgio V, Uva G, Adam JM. Integrated seismic vulnerability assessment of historical masonry churches including architectural and artistic assets based on macro-element approach. *Int J Archit Herit* 2021;15(11):1609–22.
- [56] Valente M. Seismic behavior and damage assessment of two historical fortified masonry palaces with corner towers. *Eng Fail Anal* 2022;134:106003.
- [57] Valente M. Earthquake response and damage patterns assessment of two historical masonry churches with bell tower. *Eng Fail Anal* 2023;151:107418.
- [58] Lombardi L, De Luca F. Derivation of fragility curves at design stage through linear time-history analysis. *Eng Struct* 2020;219:110900.
- [59] Wilson EI, Habibullah A. Structural analysis programs. Berkeley, CA: Computers and Structures, Inc.; 1992.
- [60] DGF (2005). Direction General of Foundations. Izmir.
- [61] Hoveidae N, Fathi A, Karimzadeh S. Seismic damage assessment of a historic masonry building under simulated scenario earthquakes: a case study for Arge-Tabriz. *Soil Dyn Earthq Eng* 2021;147:106732.
- [62] Karalar M, Yeşil M. Structural investigation of a historical masonry arch bridge under Far-Fault earthquakes. *Tehčki Vjesn* 2023;30(5):1443–50. <https://doi.org/10.17559/TV-20220711123816>.
- [63] Hrasnica, M., & Medic, S. (2012). Seismic strengthening of historical stone masonry structures in Bosnia Herzegovina. 15WCEE, Lisbon.
- [64] Türkmen, M., & Bilgin, H. (2016). Structural behavior of domed roof systems in traditional architectural buildings. Retrieved on April 27, 2016, from [website URL].
- [65] Ancheta TD, Darragh RB, Stewart JP, Seyhan E, Silva WJ, Chiou BS-J, Wooddell KE, Graves RW, Kottke AR, Boore DM, Kishida T, Donahue JL. NGA-West2 database. *Earthq Spectra* 2014;30(3):989–1005.
- [66] Kappos AJ, Manolis GD, Moschonas IF. Seismic assessment and design of R/C bridges with irregular configuration, including SSI effects. *Eng Struct* 2002;24 (10):1337–48.
- [67] Chopra AK. Dynamics of structures. Pearson Education India; 2007.
- [68] Betti M, Galano L, Vignoli A. Time-history seismic analysis of masonry buildings: a comparison between two non-linear modelling approaches. *Buildings* 2015;5 (2):597–621.
- [69] Parisi F, Balestrieri C, Varum H. Nonlinear finite element model for traditional adobe masonry. *Constr Build Mater* 2019;223:450–62.
- [70] Hökelekli E, Demir A, Ercan E, Nohutçu H, Karabulut A. Seismic assessment in a historical masonry minaret by linear and non-linear seismic analyses. *Periodica polytechnica. Civ Eng* 2020;64(2):438–48.
- [71] Pouraminian M. Multi-hazard reliability assessment of historical brick minarets. *J Build Pathol Rehabil* 2022;7(1):10.
- [72] Cattari S, Calderoni B, Calìo I, Camata G, de Miranda S, Magenes G, Saetta A. Nonlinear modeling of the seismic response of masonry structures: critical review and open issues towards engineering practice. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2022;20(4): 1939–97.
- [73] Xu D, Xie Q, Hao W. Seismic damage evaluation of historical masonry towers through numerical model. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2024;22(4):2235–66.
- [74] Ademović N, Hadzima-Nyarko M, Zagora N, Stojnović V. Various numerical modeling procedures of XIX-century masonry building. *Eng Struct* 2024;301: 117361.
- [75] Bathe, K.J. (2006). Finite element procedures. Klaus-Jurgen Bathe.
- [76] FEMA 356 (2000). "FEMA 356 Prestandard and Commentary for the Seismic Rehabilitation of Buildings", ASCE for the Federal Emergency Management Agency, Washington, D.C., November 2000.
- [77] Lopez S, D'Amato M, Ramos L, Laterza M, Lourenço PB. Simplified formulations for estimating the main frequencies of ancient masonry churches. *Front Built Environ* 2019;5:18.
- [78] ASCE 07-16 (2017). Minimum Design Loads and Associated Criteria for Buildings and Other Structures American Society of Civil, Engineers. Virginia, NV: Reston.
- [79] Circolare (2019). Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti. (2019). Istruzioni per l'applicazione dell'aggiornamento delle "Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni" di cui al decreto ministeriale 17 gennaio 2018 (Circolare 21 gennaio 2019, n. 7). Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana.
- [80] NTC-2008 (2008). Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni. D.M. 14/01/2008, S.O. n. 30 of the Official Gazette of the Italian Republic 2008.
- [81] NTC-2018 (2018). Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni. Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana, Supplemento Ordinario n. 8 del 20 febbraio 2018.
- [82] Aksoy, E., & Aydoğmuş, F. (2017). Tarihi yapıların deprem analizi ve Kargı Han örneği. Uluslararası Katılımlı 6. Tarihi Yapıların Korunması ve Güçlendirilmesi Sempozyumu, 411-419.
- [83] Şahin, E. (2019). Structural analyses and assessment of historical Çardak Caravanserai in Denizli (Master's thesis, Izmir Institute of Technology (Turkey)).
- [84] Günaydin M, Demirkir C, Altunışık AC, Gezer ED, Genc AF, Okur FY. Diagnosis and monitoring of historical timber velipaşa han building prior to restoration. *Int J Archit Herit* 2023;17(2):285–309.
- [85] Akın S, Alagoz A. Structural behavior of historical obruk inn under different earthquakes. *Chall J Struct Mech* 2024;10(1):21–33.
- [86] Kılıç Demircan R. Determination of earthquake resistance of historical masonry inn with finite element analysis. *Bull Earthq Eng* 2025:1–25.
- [87] Cuadra C, Saito T, Zavala C. Diagnosis for seismic vulnerability evaluation of historical buildings in Lima, Peru. *J Disaster Res* 2013;8(2):320–7.
- [88] D'Ayala D, Speranza E. Definition of collapse mechanisms and seismic vulnerability of historic masonry buildings. *Earthq Spectra* 2003;19(3):479–509. <https://doi.org/10.1193/1.1599896>.
- [89] Da Silva LC, Milani G, Lourenço PB. Probabilistic-based discrete model for the seismic fragility assessment of masonry structures. *Structures* 2023;52:506–23.
- [90] Negulescu C, Ulrich T, Baills A, et al. Fragility curves for masonry structures submitted to permanent ground displacements and earthquakes. *Nat Hazards* 2014;74:1461–74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-014-1253-x>.
- [91] Tarque N, Manchego A, Lovón H, Blondet M, Varum H. Experimental in-plane behaviour and drift-based fragility assessment of typical Peruvian confined masonry walls. *Constr Build Mater* 2022;341:127893.
- [92] Vicente, R. (2008). Estratégias e metodologias para intervenções de reabilitação urbana. Avaliação da vulnerabilidade e do risco sísmico do edificado da Baixa de Coimbra. PhD Thesis, Universidade de Aveiro, Portugal.
- [93] Park J, Towashiraporn P, Craig JI, Goodno BJ. Seismic fragility analysis of low-rise unreinforced masonry structures. *Eng Struct* 2009;31(1):125–37.
- [94] Caicedo D, Tomić I, Karimzadeh S, Bernardo V, Beyer K, Lourenço PB. Collapse fragility analysis of historical masonry buildings considering in-plane and out-of-plane response of masonry walls. *Eng Struct* 2024;319:118804.
- [95] Zentner I, Gündel M, Bonfils N. Fragility analysis methods: review of existing approaches and application. *Nucl Eng Des* 2017;323:245–58.
- [96] Yang J, Wang J, Zhuang H, Zhu L, Shen Y. Seismic fragility analysis for underground subway station structures considering ground motion combinations based on IDA and cloud. *Soil Dyn Earthq Eng* 2025;195:109386.
- [97] Mackie KR, Stojadinović B. Comparison of incremental dynamic, cloud, and stripe methods for computing probabilistic seismic demand models. *Structures Congress 2005. Metropolis and Beyond*; 2005. p. 1–11.
- [98] Nassirpour A, Song B, D'Ayala D. IDA & cloud method for fragility assessment of bare & infilled steel frame structures. 16th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering, 16. National Information Centre of Earthquake Engineering; 2017. p. 1–12.
- [99] Lombardi L, De Luca F, Macdonald J. Design of buildings through linear time-history analysis optimising ground motion selection: a case study for RC-MRFs. *Eng Struct* 2019;192:279–95.
- [100] Karimzadeh S, Askan A, Erberik MA, Yakut A. Seismic damage assessment based on synthetic ground motion dataset: a case study for Erzincan, Turkey. *Nat Hazards* 2018;92:1371–97.